

THE INFLUENCE OF INTERPHASE PROPERTIES & MICROSTRUCTURE ON COMPOSITE DURABILITY

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ABSTRACT

A poly(*n*-vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP) interphase material showed significant improvements in low cycle notched cross-ply compressive fatigue (one order of magnitude) and fatigue limit (10% of UCS) as compared to the conventional epoxy interphase. These enhancements appear to be the result of the inherent toughness and damage tolerance of the material as influenced by the improved inelastic properties of the thermoplastic modified interphase. Thus, it appears that the inelastic characteristics of the interphase (and not strength alone) are dominant in the understanding of compression strength and durability. However, it is unclear at this point how specific interphase properties and characteristics control the interaction of the fiber and matrix to influence the mechanics of composite strength and life.

INTRODUCTION

It has well established that the quasi-static strength of composites can be substantially altered by modification of the fiber matrix interphase region [1-10]. These dramatic changes in composite performance can be made where the interphase region makes up less than 1% of the composite volume. This region may or may not represent properties and microstructure characteristics of either the fiber, matrix or *couplant* (if present). Yet, it does possess unique properties which are tied to the microstructure that is formed when the fiber and matrix are joined during the manufacture of the laminate. It is the properties of this interphase which affect the mechanics of fiber-matrix interaction. In turn, the global performance of the composite material/structure is directly related to the nature of interaction between fiber and matrix. Thus, it is important to develop an understanding of how to join fiber and matrix so as to produce advantageous interactions which benefit composite performance. More fundamentally, understanding how particular interphase properties influence fiber-matrix interaction, and thus composite performance, is of great interest as well. These ideas require that we also know something quantitative about the dimensions and properties of this transition zone. This however, is a more difficult problem due to the scale of the interphase region (approximately 200 to 500 nm in thickness).

We however, turn our attention to the fatigue performance of these systems as influenced by these local properties changes/gradients. As these materials will eventually make their way into structures which will experience time-varying loads, questions about how material durability is affected by the character of the interphase must also be addressed. An initial look at traditional coupon durability was undertaken by Swain [8] on four different graphite fiber/polymer matrix laminates. The composites used in the study possessed four different fiber systems in conjunction with a toughened epoxy (two of the systems), an untoughened epoxy (one of the systems) and a thermoplastic (one of the systems) matrix. In each material system the fiber and matrix remained the same and only the interphase was altered. The interphase was systematically modified for the four different fiber systems through the addition of fiber surface treatments and sizings as well as their combination. In this work, fully reversed ($R=-1$) fatigue of notched $[0/90]_8$ at 75% of their

ultimate static compression strength revealed that with changes in the level of surface-treatment, only small differences in fatigue life were observed. This is in spite of significant enhance of quasi-static strength(s) for increased levels of treatment.

The only significant improvements in durability were observed for changes in sizing materials; an "organic sizing" was substituted for the "standard epoxy sizing" on a 100% surface treated fiber. Mindful that these two systems possessed similar quasi-static strengths, but slightly different fiber dominated moduli, the organic sized fiber composite survived 2×10^6 cycles as compared to a life of 10^4 cycles at the same stress level for the composite with the standard epoxy size. It was however, not clear how the interphase influenced this substantial change in performance.

Subramanian [9] investigated the effects of interphases on the tensile static and dynamic fatigue performance of $[0/90]_S$ cross-ply laminates. The material used in this study was also that employed by Swain [8]. Subramanian also observed differences in performance of the organic sized fiber laminates as compared to those composites where the fibers were sized with an epoxy. In $R=0.1$ fatigue of the cross-ply laminates, the PVP interphase materials performed better in low cycle fatigue, while the epoxy interphase material showed greater durability in high cycle fatigue. Subramanian concluded that the above observed phenomena were the result of one fundamental characteristic: the efficiency of stress transfer between the fiber and matrix as influenced by the interphase. By including the efficiency parameter, η , in the analysis of tensile strength and, likewise, tensile fatigue, Subramanian was able to predict performance with good agreement.

The following discussion attempts to add to this body of knowledge by examining the compressive fatigue durability of these systems as affected by contrasting interphases. We attempt to isolate the failure mechanism which controls life of the composite and connect that with the associated effect on fiber matrix interaction as influenced by the developed interphase.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Material Systems: The 8 & 3 Series Composite Materials

The present study employs materials obtained from McDonnell Aircraft Co., through Dexter Hysol, under the Air Force program "Development of Ultralightweight Materials." We employ the two materials employed by Swain and Subramanian which contain the Courtaulds Research Apollo 45-850, 5 micron diameter carbon fiber in Dexter Hysol's HC 9106-3 di-, tri- and tetra-functional epoxy toughened with the thermoplastic PES. The thermoplastic poly-ethersylophone (PES) toughening agent, present in this epoxy matrix, is presumed to phase separate out once cured. These panels were fabricated via autoclave by Dexter Hysol.

For convenience, the two systems of interest are named 810A, and 810O as taken by the nomenclature of Swain [8]. The leading 8 represents the matrix system used HC 9106-3 and are referred to as the 8 series composites. The trailing 10 denote the level of surface treatment, 100%. The A and O designate the type of sizing. Details of the oxidative surface-treatment levels are not known but are related to a standardized degree of application, designated 100%, and deemed *optimum* by the manufacturer. Lesko et al. [4] identified these sizings with permission from Courtaulds. The A sizing is an unreacted bisphenol-A based epoxy and the O sizing is the linear and amorphous thermoplastic, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). Again, these are the sizings, incorporated in Swain's and Subramanian's work, in which the A sizing is the "standard epoxy sizing" and the O sizing is the "organic size". These sizings were reported to be present at approximately 0.7 weight percent of the fiber.

Clearly the nature of these two sizings are compositionally very different. The PVP is a linear thermoplastic which appears to act as a diluent, where as the A size will eventually react into the network of the epoxy to form a microstructure not unlike the bulk matrix. Evidence of these differences are noted by examining the microstructures form with their composites. The microstructures of the 810A and 810O interphases were revealed by an etching technique [4]. Under identical etching conditions the epoxy sized fibers did not reveal as distinct an interphase region as that observed in the PVP sized composite. The epoxy sized composite shows an irregular interface region between fiber and matrix. Particular regions about the epoxy sized fiber possess irregular gaps between fiber and matrix. On other portions of the A sized fiber perimeter, matrix material is observed in direct apposition to the fiber. In direct contrast, the PVP interphase extended into the matrix approximately 10% of the fiber diameter, or $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$. Although this

interphase was readily observed around many of the fibers, it was not always uniform in thickness for each fiber. In some cases, an interphase region observed is somewhat smaller or not present at all. The formation of a varied morphology in the PVP interphase might be explained through the simple process of diffusion. The maximum processing temperature of these composites was 177°C and, as previously stated, the T_g of the PVP size is approximately 109°C. Hence, the PVP is well into its rubbery regime and potentially able to disperse/dissolve into the epoxy. This is not to neglect any other driving forces producing interaction of the two polymers. It has been established that the PVP is generally miscible with the matrix [10].

A subsequent series of laminates were produced as a result of the findings and work of Swain [8] on the 8 series materials described above. The 3 series composites, as they are now named, contain essentially the same Courtauld's fibers noted above except in Hercules *untoughened* aerospace epoxy 3501-6 matrix. These laminates were manufactured by Hercules. The 3501-6 epoxy possesses a tensile modulus of 0.64 Msi, tensile strength of 10.0 ksi and an elongation at break of 1.7%. The G_{Ic} of the neat material is 130 J/m² and shows a T_g of 185°C. The nomenclature for the two systems is similar to that of the 8 series composites where the 8 is replaced with the 3, now representing the 3501-6 epoxy matrix.

Quasi-Static Properties of the 8 and 3 Series Composites

For the purposes of this discussion we will only sight the quasi-static characteristics of the 8 and 3 series composites as reported elsewhere [8-10]. These characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Comparing the strength and toughness of the A and O interphases, for the two different epoxy matrix systems, it is clear that the PVP interphase produces a "better" material. These data will compliment the conclusions developed in fatigue durability study to follow.

Table 1. A summary of the quasi-static properties of the 8 and 3 series composites.

	Toughened Matrix HC 9106-3		Untoughened Matrix 3501-6	
	PVP Size 8100	Epoxy Size 810A	PVP Size 3100	Epoxy Size 310A
Unidirectional Tension				
Strength (ksi)	444	407	416	410
Failure Strain (%)	1.66	1.31	1.57	1.37
Unidirectional Compression				
Strength (ksi)	160	106	180	186
Failure Strain (%)	0.74	0.45	0.93	0.79
Transverse Flexure				
Strength (ksi)	18.3	11.9	15.5	10.7
Failure Strain (%)	1.34	0.91	0.91	0.97
Iosipescu Shear				
Strength (ksi)	10.6	8.7	6.5	5.3
Failure Strain (%)	1.15	0.81	0.52	0.35
Interlaminar Toughness				
Mode I (J/m ²)	434	303	472	247
Mode II (J/m ²)	666	527	464	402
[0/90]8s Laminate				
Notched Compression Strength (ksi)	42.8	42.3	45.5	45.3
Unnotched Compression Strength (ksi)	72.6	71.8	87.6	87.1

Description of the Fatigue Durability Study

Two specimens from each of the two interphase conditions were available for characterization of the virgin notched properties. Those data are included in Table 1. The notched specimens measured 1" wide, 6" long and nominally 0.16" in thickness. A 0.25" diameter center-hole notch was machined in the geometric center of the 1" wide, 6" long specimen. The remaining notched specimens were reserved for fatigue tests for which the static strengths provided a reference from which to select the fatigue load levels. Although two specimens is considerably low for attempting to characterize strength, the limited amount of material available forced this decision. This test procedure was also used for the assessment of residual strength of the notched materials.

Antibuckling guides were not used in performing the compression tests. To ensure that buckling would not figure into the compression failure of these laminates, an unsupported length of 2.25" was selected based on the work of Swain [8]. This unsupported length did not yield any failures which exhibited buckling. A fatigue ratio of $R=10$ using a sinusoidal wave form at 10 Hz was selected for this study. The compression-compression fatigue, as opposed to fully reversed fatigue, best allowed the authors to isolate compressive damage mechanisms as they relate to the interphase.

Dye penetrent enhanced x-ray radiography and video monitoring of the surface damage were two non-destructive techniques employed to monitor the damage developed during the various stages of the specimen life. These "damage" monitoring techniques will assist in developing a fuller understanding of the $R=10$ the damage mechanisms and how they may distinguish themselves by changes in interphase properties.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

S-N Curve, 8 Series

As with the work of Swain [7] and Subramanian [9], substantial differences between the performance of the A and O fiber sized composites is observed. Reviewing the S-N curve for the 8 series compression-compression, $R=10$, fatigue, a best fit line through each of the data sets assists in delineation of the difference in performance of the A and O interphases, as shown in Figure 1. The applied cyclic stress level are presented as a percentage of their ultimate notched compression strength level as reported in Table 1. The 810A composite exhibited a slightly lower rate of life reduction with increasing load level. However, all lives recorded for 810A, with the exception of that at the 85% of the ultimate compression strength (UCS) of the notched laminate, are less than those measured for the PVP sizing. The 810O composite shows relatively good agreement to the fit that reveals a greater sensitivity to load level. At lower load levels it appears to perform better than its epoxy sized counterpart. A fatigue limit, at approximately 73% UCS, is recorded for the 810O. By the limited data set of the 810A, a best possible fatigue limit is potentially expected at a load level no greater than at 65% UCS and positively identified at 60% UCS. Thus, there appears to exist a considerable difference in fatigue limit between the 810A and 810O. However, a test for statistical significance between these assumed linear fits suggests that they are essentially the same both in slope and intercept. (The failure of the null hypothesis, that the slopes are not the same, may have also been affected by the poor linear fit of the data for the 810A material.)

S-N Curve, 3 Series

As with the results of the 8 series composites, substantial differences in lives exist between the PVP interphase materials and the epoxy interphase materials, as shown in Figure 2. An assumed linear fit to the low cycle fatigue data, from specimens which were not interrupted, appear to indicate that the PVP interphase provides an order of magnitude improvement in life. The significance of this difference between the linear fits to this data are proven to a 90% level of confidence. This difference is still maintained in light of the similarity in the 310A & O unidirectional compression strengths as well as notched compression strengths. Thus, one might consider the inherent compression strength (axial performance) in conjunction with the off-axis characteristics of the material to understand the difference in fatigue performance between the A and the O interphase composites. Recall that essentially all of the inelastic off-axis characteristics of the O interphase were greater than that of the A interphase for both the 8 and 3 series composites (Table 1). This data might also be viewed as remarkable in light of the fact that the quasi-static compression strength of these two laminates are nearly identical.

An apparent fatigue limit is recorded for the 3100 at 65% of UCS, which is below that measured for the 8100 (at 74% UCS). This is potentially not unexpected due to the difference in the matrix toughness between the 8 and 3 series composites. Once again, the transition from low cycle fatigue to high cycle fatigue characteristics, appears to take place over a small window of load level as was observed for the 8 series. At 68% of UCS the 3100 fails at 10^5 cycles. Radiographs of the 3100 at the 65% load level will reveal little evidence of damage which might be considered detrimental to the life of the laminate (discussed in the following section). Considering the 310A at the 65% of UCS load level, there is at the very least, an order of magnitude difference in life. Cycling the 310A composite at 62.5% of UCS does not reveal a fatigue limit. Thus, it is possible that there exists a difference in fatigue limit between the two interphases as was noted in the 8 series composites. However, the difference in the A and O fatigue limits are smaller but can not be quantified at this writing due to the limited amount of material available.

Source of the Improvements to Fatigue Durability

The above results suggest that the interphase does play a role in the durability of these materials. But, how does the interphase play a role in the fatigue failure process? We might begin to address this conundrum by considering the two primary factors which influence the strength and life of notched composites. According to Kortschot and Beaumont, the strength of a notched composite is controlled either by the ability of the laminate to relieve the stress concentration by the growth of longitudinal splits (LS) or by the intrinsic strength of the material [11]. Thus, an investigation of the growth rate of the longitudinal 0° ply splits which extend tangent to hole's edge. This was accomplished by interrupting fatigue tests at particular intervals and assessing the split length by x-ray radiography. Compiling this data for the different interphases in the 3 series composites, it appears that there is no effect of interphase on the LS growth rate, as demonstrated in Figure 3.

Thus, one must now examine the second feature which could control the strength of a notched laminate: the intrinsic *strength* of the material. It is evident from the review of quasi-static properties that the compression strength of the unidirectional 310A and 3100 composite materials are nearly identical. This is also true for the notched $[0/90]_8$ s laminates (see Table 1). However, we also recognize that the failure strain and the interlaminar toughness of the PVP interphase materials is consistently higher for most all modes of deformation. Thus, the authors suggest that it is not necessarily the inherent strength of the composites which control the laminate strength but *the intrinsic toughness* of the PVP interphase material which enhances the life of the 8100 and 3100 notched laminates.

This inference is supported when considering the dominate failure mode, the growth of ply buckling from the hole's edge perpendicular to the loading axis, which appears to control the residual strength and life of these laminates. Surface ply buckling (SPB) was recorded by video and revealed distinguishing attributes for each of the two interphases. For example, it was observed at a load level of 70% of the ultimate compression strength that the 3100 material initiates SPB at approximately 10,000 cycles as compared to 3,000 cycles for the 310A material as shown in Figure 4. The PVP interphase material possesses a particular advantage over the conventional epoxy sized material in the reduced rate of SPB growth. In addition, this data also suggested the critical length at which unstable growth of ply buckling occurred was greater for the PVP interphase than for the conventional epoxy interphase. This may suggest that the 8100 and 3100 materials possessed a greater *apparent* critical K (stress intensity factor).

It was generally observed at the other load levels that the O interphase material, exhibiting longer lives, initiated SPB later on in life and grew at a slower rate with cycles. This was also generally true for the 8 series material as well. Once again, the direct influence the individual interphases had on these phenomena are not understood at this writing. The authors suggest that the interphase may play a role in the inherent toughness or ductility of the composite material which allows the O interphase material particularly to behave in a more damage tolerant manner. There is much evidence from the quasi-static performance which supports this assertion (see Table 1).

In summary, the authors conclude that it is *not* the LS splitting which controls the difference in lives between the A and O interphase materials, but the inherent characteristics of the material which dominate their fatigue response. Kortschot and Beaumont claim that the compression strength of notched laminates is controlled by either one LS length or by inherent material *strength*. The authors claim that it is not merely the inherent *strength* of the material that has influenced the durability if these varied interphase system but, more exactly, the toughness or damage tolerance of

the material. Once again, the explicit role in these improvements to material toughness is not known at this writing and requires further detailed knowledge of the interphase and its properties.

CONCLUSIONS & REMARKS

This discussion demonstrated the influence the interphase and its microstructure on the compression fatigue performance of continuous fiber composites. The investigation focused on two contrasting materials modified through interphase properties: one derived from the linear thermoplastic PVP fiber size and the other influenced by an unreacted epoxy fiber size. In an effort to demonstrate that these interphase effects were reproducible, two sets of composites were examined, one with an untoughened epoxy (3 series) and the other with a toughened epoxy matrix (the 8 series). In both cases the fiber remained essentially the same with the only difference being in the interphase as altered by the two contrasting sizings/coatings. These contrasting interphases showed drastically different performance for both static and dynamic loading. In particular, the PVP interphase demonstrated advantages to static performance as summarized in Table 1. More importantly, the PVP interphase also demonstrated considerable and significant improvements to compressive fatigue performance. These enhancements are claimed to be the result of the inherent toughness and damage tolerance of the material as influenced by the altered inelastic properties of the PVP interphase. In virtually all trials the composite with the PVP interphase possessed increased toughness/ductility as compared to those composites with the epoxy interphase. However, much work remains in an attempt to develop the fundamental description of how specific interphase properties and characteristics control the interaction of the fiber and matrix to affect the mechanics of composite strength and life.

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Figure 1. Applied gross compression stress (as a % of the ultimate notched $[0/90]_S$ compression strength) versus the cycles (log of n), for the 810A and O materials under $R=10$ fatigue.

Figure 2. Applied gross compression stress (as a % of the ultimate notched $[0/90]_S$ compression strength) versus the cycles (log of n), for the 310A and O materials under $R=10$ fatigue.

Figure 3. Longitudinal split length growth characteristics for the 3 series materials from x-ray radiography data.

Figure 4. Surface ply buckling growth characteristics for the 3 series composites fatigued at 70% of UCS.